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WP5 Integration & Testing

First Version of the Public D5.5 Engagement and Training Infrastructure

ENIGMA: Endorsing safeguarding, protection, and
provenance management of cultural heritage

ENIGMA CONSORTIUM

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¹ **R** = Document, Report, **DMP** = Data Management Plan, **OTHER** = Other

² **PU** = Public, **SEN** = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

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ABBREVIATIONS

Term	Explanation
API	Application Programming Interface
CG	Cultural Good
CH	Cultural Heritage
CMS	Content Management System
DBMS	Data Base Management System
DL	Deep Learning
DO	Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Objectives
DoA	Description of Action
DT	Digital Twin
EO	Earth Observation
GIS	Geographic Information System
GUI	Graphical User Interface
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEA	Law Enforcement Agency
ML	Machine Learning
RBAC	Robust Role-based Access Control
SBE	Scenario Building Engine
SO	Scientific & Innovation Objectives
TG	Target Groups
UAI	Unique Authenticity Identifier
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ENIGMA project aims to safeguard, monitor and manage cultural heritage by integrating advanced technologies, with a particular emphasis on illicit trafficking and trading of CGs. Within this context ENIGMA developed cohesive and complementary web-based tools useful for specific stakeholders for harnessing and preserving CH assets. As part of WP5 Integration & Testing, D5.5 logically builds on the WP5 sequence that provides a Testing and Integration Methodology (D5.1) and The Final version of the ENIGMA Platform (D5.4). Building on these, D5.5 provides an overview of public engagement through its training infrastructure where D5.5 seeks to optimize stakeholder engagement through developing a clear and concise training infrastructure and manuals.

D5.5 examines how the ENIGMA platform enhances user engagement through accessible data, contributing to the success of the platform, its tools, and the overall project. D5.5 contains a brief explanatory section of what the consortium discerns as public engagement and training infrastructure as a framework for training stakeholders in using the ENIGMA platform and tools. D5.5 provides a concise overview of the tools developed by the consortium and details the training available to stakeholders and target groups (TGs) for optimal use of the ENIGMA platform. The tools consist of the 3D Reconstruction Tool, Provenance Research Tool, Crowdsourcing Tool, Web Crawler, Earth Observation Toolkit and Scenario Building Engine. Each of these holds a particular value for each stakeholder broadly defined as LEAs, Archaeologists, and Curators. To enhance public engagement of the stakeholders, ENIGMA relies on a user-based and user-friendly semi-dynamic environment, as a virtual classroom. Within the ENIGMA virtual classroom each stakeholder can navigate through multi-modal forms of training information (e.g., PDF manuals, video instructions, VR environment). The ENIGMA web-based platform allows for easy registration to enhance stakeholder engagement, while providing a virtual classroom to optimize learning outcomes of the tools tailored to each of the stakeholders' requirements. The last section contains a training narrative for each tool and includes the manuals that will form part of the training infrastructure.

1. INTRODUCTION

Deliverable D5.5 focuses on the initial development of the training and public engagement infrastructure and presents their initial versions. The public engagement

tool entails a user-friendly web-based application where the users can report information regarding potential illegal excavations, or looted buildings.

The training infrastructure will offer access to educational/training material for the use of the ENIGMA developed tools as standalone materials and through a VR environment, access to real world examples, a best practices booklet, and a repository hosted on a trusted site.

The purpose is to provide a web-based platform where different stakeholders and TGs can engage with innovative technologies in an integrated and cohesive platform to empower LEAs, archaeologists and curators, among others, and fostering complementary cross-collaborations to combat illegal excavations, illicit trading and trafficking of heritage assets and sites of cultural significance.

1.1 Purpose of D5.5

WP5 is crucial to ENIGMA's mission, ensuring the functionality, reliability, and impact of its solutions in combating illicit trade of cultural goods (CGs) and monitoring heritage sites against human-induced threats. Yet, a key factor in the success and impact of these tools primarily lies in their accessibility, appeal, and convenience to stakeholders. D5.5, as the Public Engagement and Training Infrastructure, establishes a strong foundation for ENIGMA to achieve its objectives through a user-friendly Graphical User Interface (GUI) that serves as a sustainable, cost-effective decision-support platform. Such provisions help fulfill the ENIGMA objectives as outlined in the DoA (SO3: KPI 1.16, KPI 1.17, KPI 1.19; DO1: KPI 2.1, KPI 2.2, KPI 2.3, KPI 2.4).

D5.5 offers an overview of the stakeholder engagement, and the training infrastructure provided for third-party users of the ENIGMA Platform. Based on these ENIGMA and stakeholder requirements, a training infrastructure is provided for the following ENIGMA tools (Figure 1):

1. The 3D Reconstruction Tool
2. The Provenance Research Tool (including the documentation tool)
3. The Crowdsourcing Tool (the manual will be added in the final version in D5.6)
4. The Web Crawler (the manual will be added in the final version in D5.6)
5. The Earth Observation Tool
6. The Scenario Building Engine

Figure 1. Overview of ENIGMA Toolbox which require Training Infrastructure

This deliverable defines a public engagement framework and provides an overview of the training infrastructure offered, including the VR environment, website access and best practices. To maximize public engagement, two main infrastructures have been designed and developed. The first version that has been created provides two main components. The public engagement infrastructure to let the public interact and provide insights in a crowdsourcing environment and the training infrastructure that offers the main training space incorporating easy to use access to material and a semi-dynamic, user-friendly GUI, as a virtual classroom, aided with the same training manuals as the main training infrastructure's backbone. The training infrastructure in this first version allows stakeholders to access multimodal training materials, such as PDF manuals, video tutorials, tailored to diverse learning styles and stakeholder requirements. The web-based GUI equally simplifies registration and optimizes learning outcomes by providing targeted training resources. The training infrastructure adheres to a specific design and incorporates a pedagogical narrative. Training manuals for each of the tools are provided with the aim of guiding and training stakeholders on how to utilize the ENIGMA tools.

2. PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT INFRASTRUCTURE

The ENIGMA public engagement infrastructure is designed to leverage crowdsourced information by providing user-friendly tools for reporting potential illegal excavation sites or looted buildings, based on location, time, and images. The tool will also give to the users the ability to check existing stolen CGs databases, such as the Interpol's stolen works of art database, FBI's national stolen art file database, etc. Since integration mechanisms for these databases are not available, the tool will provide direct links to stolen cultural goods databases, allowing users to access them through their original platforms and applications. The crowdsourcing tool will be based on a geographic information system. An overview of the architecture as designed and implemented is described in the following section.

2.1 Design and Implementation of the Architecture

The main objective of the crowdsourcing tool is to report potential illegal excavation sites or looted buildings providing the corresponding spatiotemporal information, along with the images that have been collected. All the information collected using this tool will be reviewed by the component authorities and the "true" cases will be flagged and will be taken into account to hotspot analysis. This analysis will be available to LEA Officers and the archaeologists/experts. To implement the described concept, the mechanisms to manage location and content, images or other documents management, has been established. The architecture consists of the components in the "backend" to manage the geospatial information and the components in the front end to analyze and visualize the hot spot analysis result (Figure 2).

Figure 2: General components diagram

The implemented ArcGIS Enterprise system will be based on a 3 Tier architecture. This architecture will have as its basic components the existence of one or more web application servers (Business logic Tier), a server for the Database Management System (DBMS) (Database Management Tier) and a presentation system (Presentation Tier) for the data to be managed.

- Database and Geodata Management Tier (Data Management Tier)
- Application Tier (Application Tier-Business Logic Tier)
- Presentation Tier

This architecture will provide the capabilities for data deposition, data retrieval and the ability to develop user interfaces for managing, analysing and reporting both descriptive and spatial data at one or more workstations. The schema of the described architecture is shown in the following diagram (Figure 3).

Figure 3: General architecture of the System and the infrastructure implemented

The main relational database management system is the same that is used for the ENIGMA fast documentation database and is based on PostgreSQL. The authentication mechanism is only available for the administrators to manage the reported data. The crowdsourcing process is managed without authentication since the tool does not request any user entitled access.

Based on the above scheme, the "Data Management Tier" is responsible for the RDBMS database management system. In this tier, a Database Server Virtual Machine was implemented to host the Central Database Infrastructure, as well as all databases that incorporate geospatial information.

At the same time, the Geographic Information System server infrastructure and the infrastructure for interfacing with other data management systems will be served by the "Application Tier". ArcGIS Enterprise is a Geographic Information System (GIS) platform designed to analyze spatial data, generate interactive maps, and drive location-based insights. The ArcGIS Database forms the backbone for storing and managing spatial data, enabling users to organize, query, and analyze complex datasets efficiently. The combination of the two tiers is the infrastructure that will provide the support for data and geoprocessing access from the interfaces of the end users.

At the Presentation tier, through the infrastructure of the geospatial-temporal data server, and in combination with the user and content management system (from the Application

Tier), user interfaces for accessing Web GIS applications are provided to users. One is the Responsive web GIS crowd sourcing tool, the second one is the Main authoritative crowdsourcing data review and management, and the third one is the application to visualize the spatiotemporal analysis of the valid data to LEA Officers and archaeologist/experts.

2.2 The Corresponding Tools for the Public Engagement

The crowdsourcing reporting tool is accessible through a WebGIS. The user doesn't need to be registered to use the tool. During the submission page a notice is displaying an alert that only users over 18 can submit a report. They will be able to create a report that will include the location of the site data input (either by using the GPS coordinates of the mobile device, or by selecting the location on a map), upload some images, write a comment and if they want to provide their email address to submit the report. During the submission modern human verification techniques will be used to avoid potential spam. Following the submission the user will get confirmation directly on the form that the report has been successfully submitted.

In this context an application that is web based but incorporating responsiveness support to mobile devices has been developed. Furthermore, the tool uses GIS technologies to enhance the geolocation process.

The information that the crowdsourcing management tool maintains is created by public users into a simple form that reports an event and considers the location as well as the time that the event occurred (Figure 4).

The screenshot shows a web form titled "REPORTING" with three main sections:

- 1. Enter Information:** Contains a dropdown menu for "TYPE OF INCIDENT", a text input field for "COMMENTS", and a date picker for "DATE".
- 2. Select Location:** Includes a "Search" button, a "Lat/Lon" input field, and a "Find address or place" input field with a "Locate Me" button.
- 3. Complete Form:** Features a satellite map of a region with labels for "Eliada", "Central Macedonia", and "Thessaloniki". Below the map is a "Submit Entry" button.

Figure 4: Responsive Event reporting form for public participation

All this information is uploaded directly to the main system and is provided to the corresponding authority. Only the component authority (e.g., Ministry of Culture, Law enforcement agencies) has access to the submitted data. They are able by using the management interface to process the data, check the reports and decide whether the reports are valid or not. The map will also include the details of the report (images, comments, etc.).

The data storage will be managed by the component authority. The users will not have access to the data and will not have the ability to view, modify, or erase the data they have submitted. The final output of the processing is implemented as a map with hot spots that could only be accessed by registered authenticated users (e.g., archaeologist or experts working under the ministry of culture, Law Enforcement Agencies officers) that have access to the ENIGMA provenance research tools.

The crowdsourcing management interface is also incorporated as 1st version in the interim ENIGMA platform and will be fully deployed and tested until the final version of the platform. An example of the crowd reports management interface is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: User Interface to manage crowd reported events

3. TRAINING INFRASTRUCTURE

A complex project like ENIGMA requires a specialized training infrastructure that accommodates the diverse needs of stakeholders. Thus, the ENIGMA project has developed a semi-dynamic, web-based training infrastructure designed to engage stakeholders and TGs. Training modalities include a semi-dynamic VR classroom environment with guided tutorials, interactive scenarios, and downloadable manuals. This multi-tiered infrastructure ensures that stakeholders can access training resources aligned with their requirements. The training framework is based on providing easy-to-understand and step-by-step guidelines for users with the aim to support stakeholders at various digital literacy levels.

3.1 Website Access to Training Material

The infrastructure that in parallel with the VR training infrastructure will support the end users is designed and deployed as a 1st version through the main ENIGMA web site. The end users will have the ability to request access from the coordinator of the project and after that they will get the corresponding access to view the training material (Figure 6).

Figure 6 Main menu to access training digital space and login

The website serves as the central hub for accessing all necessary content, including links to the VR platform, ENIGMA tool training materials, best practices, and real-world examples (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Training web site section

3.2 VR Training

In recent years, the integration of VR technology into educational and training programs has demonstrated significant potential in enhancing learning experiences. VR provides immersive, interactive environments that allow users to engage with content beyond the capabilities of traditional methods. This section outlines the implementation of a VR platform specifically designed to support the ENIGMA project's educational modules, providing stakeholders with an innovative and engaging way to acquire critical knowledge and skills.

This section outlines the design and development of the VR platform used for delivering the core modules of the ENIGMA project. The platform aims to provide an engaging and effective training environment for key stakeholders, including law enforcement agencies, cultural institutions, researchers, and policymakers. Through learning material, users will gain a deeper understanding on using the ENIGMA tools.

By leveraging VR technology, the platform will facilitate experiential learning, allowing users to explore virtual representations of cultural goods in a controlled environment. The VR-based approach will enhance user comprehension in CH protection. This will not only improve training outcomes but also foster collaboration and knowledge sharing among various stakeholders.

This section provides an in-depth overview of the VR platform's implementation process, including the system architecture, content development, user experience design, and deployment strategies. It highlights the technological components that will be integrated, to ensure that the platform aligns with the ENIGMA project's objectives.

The significance of this initiative lies in its potential to revolutionize CH education and management by bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. The VR platform will serve as a valuable resource for training professionals involved in CH protection, equipping them with the skills needed to address contemporary challenges such as illicit trafficking, and unauthorized excavations.

In conclusion, the implementation of the VR platform for the ENIGMA project represents a pioneering effort to harness emerging technologies for cultural heritage. By offering an immersive learning environment, the platform will contribute to the overall success of the ENIGMA project, ensuring that CH remains protected for future generations.

3.2.1 VR Platform Architecture

The VR platform architecture is designed to provide a robust, scalable, and immersive experience for users, ensuring seamless interaction with CH content. The architecture is designed for use in a web environment. The software stack includes development environments such as Unity 3D for creating immersive simulations, alongside 3D modelling tools for artifact and environment design.

The platform features a content management system (CMS) that allows user role-based access for customizing and deploying training modules, with built-in version control and auditing capabilities. The user interface (UI) and experience (UX) design emphasize

intuitive navigation menus, featuring an avatar-style third person view for enhanced engagement. The platform offers multi-language support and accessibility features to cater to diverse users, along with a mini map for quick navigation within a detailed 3D environment, providing an authentic and engaging educational experience.

User management and access control are critical components of the VR platform to ensure secure and personalized experiences. The platform implements robust role-based access control (RBAC), enabling users to be assigned specific permissions based on their roles, such as administrators, educators, or trainees. Logging mechanisms are integrated to track user activity, providing insights into interactions, training progress, and potential security events. Additionally, the system offers comprehensive avatar creation features, allowing users to personalize their virtual representations with customizable attributes and preferences. These avatars enhance immersion and engagement by enabling users to navigate the VR environment in a personalized and interactive manner.

The image displays a user interface for account management, divided into three main sections:

- Create your account:** Located on the left, it features the heading "Create your account" and the subtext "Sign-up with your email". Below this is a prominent blue button labeled "Create an account". At the bottom of this section, it asks "Have an account?" followed by a "Log in" link.
- Signup with your email:** The central section is titled "Signup with your email" with the instruction "Please fill in the details below". It contains four input fields: "First name *", "Email Address *", "Password *", and "Confirm Password *". Each field has a corresponding icon (envelope for email, padlock for password). A blue "Sign Up" button is positioned at the bottom of this section.
- Sign in:** Located on the right, it is titled "Sign in" with the subtext "Sign in with your email". It includes two input fields: "Email *" and "Password *", each with an icon. Below these fields are a "Remember Me" checkbox and a "Forgot Password?" link. A blue "LOGIN" button is at the bottom of this section.

Figure 8: Easy signup, register and change password user interfaces

Figure 9: Sample A of Online 3D environment

Figure 10: Sample B of the Online 3D environment

3.2.2 Content Design and Module Implementation

The content design and module implementation of the VR platform are meticulously structured to provide an engaging and educational experience for users. Each module is developed based on instructional design principles to ensure effective knowledge transfer and skills development.

The design process begins with a thorough analysis of learning objectives and user requirements, which inform the creation storytelling elements. These elements will be integrated into the VR environment to provide an immersive and experiential learning experience. To ensure a dynamic learning experience, the modules incorporate a mix of instructional strategies, such as documents, videos, and guided tutorials.

The implementation of the modules follows a phased approach, beginning with prototype development and user testing to gather feedback and make iterative improvements. The final modules will be deployed through the VR platform with easy access for stakeholders via the ENIGMA website.

The following modules and content will be designed (Table 1: VR modules):

REQUIREMENTS	STATUS	PRIORITY/BENEFIT
Module 1: “Main content navigation room”	Approved	Critical
Module 2: “The Museum 3D interface”	Approved	Critical
Module 3: “Avatar Selection”	Approved	Critical
Module 4: “User management and levels”	Approved	Critical
Module 5: “Chat mechanism”	Approved	Nice to have
Module 6: “multi-language support”	Approved	Nice to have
Module 7: “Mini map for quick navigation”	Approved	Critical
Module 8: “Background music”	Approved	Nice to have
Module 9: “Web based access through browser”	Approved	Critical
Content 1: “Provenance research tool”	Approved	Critical
Content 2: “Scenario Building Engine”	Approved	Critical
Content 3: “Earth Observation Toolkit”	Approved	Critical
Content 4: “3D CG reconstruction tool from fragments”	Approved	Critical
Content 5: “Crowd sourcing tool”	Approved	Critical

Table 1: VR modules

3.2.3 Implementation Process

The implementation process of the VR platform follows a structured, phased approach to ensure successful deployment and adoption by stakeholders. Following the high-level

requirements above, the next phase involves the development of a prototype, where core functionalities are implemented and tested. This iterative development process allows for regular feedback from users, enabling continuous refinement and improvement of the 3D experience.

Following the prototype stage, full-scale development commences, focusing on the integration of the content management system, security features, and user analytics tools. Rigorous testing is conducted to ensure stability, performance, and compatibility across various VR devices and platforms. Usability testing is performed with a diverse group of end-users to identify potential challenges and optimize the user experience.

Once the platform is deemed ready for deployment, a phased rollout strategy is implemented. Comprehensive training sessions and support materials are provided to ensure a smooth transition for users.

Post-deployment, continuous monitoring and support are provided to address any technical issues, gather user feedback, and introduce new features and improvements. Regular updates and maintenance cycles ensure that the VR platform remains aligned with the evolving needs of the ENIGMA project and its stakeholders.

3.3 Real World Examples

This training material that will enrich the training infrastructure as content will include real-world examples designed to bridge the gap between theory and practice. By exploring relevant scenarios, case studies, and hands-on examples, learners gain insights into how concepts are applied in real-world situations. These examples are tailored to be similar with the challenges and opportunities professionals face in their respective industries, ensuring the content is relevant, engaging, and actionable.

Learning is most effective when it is connected to real-world experiences. That is why this training material goes beyond abstract concepts, focusing on scenarios that reflect actual workplace challenges and opportunities. These examples are crafted to help the end users to:

- Apply theoretical knowledge to solve real problems.
- Build practical skills through relatable situations.
- Enhance decision-making and critical thinking by understanding how professionals handle real-world complexities.

Throughout this material, the end user will encounter diverse examples and case studies as defined from the ENIGMA project, helping the stakeholders to build confidence in their ability to turn learning into action.

The material will be accessible under the training section of the web site and only by authorized users. In Figure 11 the website section that will provide access to the material is presented.

Figure 11: Training material – Real world examples material filtered

3.4 ENIGMA Tools Presentation

Based on stakeholder feedback, ENIGMA developed tools for monitoring the illicit trafficking of artefacts (These tools are still in the testing and implementation phase and prone to amendments). As a brief overview of the tools is described below:

The **3D reconstruction tool** is designed for fast reconstruction of incomplete, or damaged objects by implementing DL methods. The tool creates 3D models based on a limited number 2D images and text input. It is tailored for easy 'on the spot' application by LEAs.

The **provenance research tool** is offered through the ENIGMA platform as a web-based GUI tailored to different user roles, such as LEAs and archaeologists. Through the tool, stakeholders can use features like remote sensing, AI-powered similarity checking (incorporating UAI) public participation tools and EO alert on potential illegal excavations. Users can input CG details, upload documents and photos, and assign jobs to experts to obtain supplementary provenance information. The tool facilitates seamless

collaboration by tracing CGs involved in or suspected of illicit trafficking for enhancing provenance research.

The **crowdsourcing tool** is designed to gather input from the public, primarily through forms that operate via mobile devices. A web-based GUI enables users to report events involving potential illegal actions on the field of looted buildings, fostering public engagement in CH preservation.

The **web crawler and data sharing system** incorporate advanced algorithms to extract metadata, including images, videos, and other relevant information, from various databases. As such, the tool ensures a rapid and continuous data flow. Once extracted, the data will be securely stored in the internal ENIGMA database, providing a centralized resource for further analysis, research, and stakeholder collaboration.

The **earth observation toolkit** aims to improve the early and precise detection of potential threats or damage to CH sites. It monitors specific sites for potential illegal excavations by employing satellite imagery analysis. The EO tool allows multiple users to view, search, and retrieve information related to these sites, enabling efficient collaboration and enhanced monitoring of potential threats to archaeological sites.

The **scenario building engine** is primarily designed to function as a standalone application, intended to model and map both current and future LEA operating processes. It facilitates the modelling and simulating of procedures and operating scenarios. The SBE allows LEA officers to design and analyze workflows, ensuring that their responses to illicit activities are effective and efficient. In collaboration with archaeologists and experts, LEAs can assess and optimize workflow performance for greater operational success.

3.5 Best Practices

The ENIGMA best practice examples play a crucial role in guiding users through the effective use of digital applications. These best practice examples act as illustrative applications of the tools to provide consistency and efficiency. Since the tools remain in the testing and implementation phase, the best practice examples are still under development and will evolve along the process to further enhance the user experience of stakeholders. Therefore, in this version the best practice booklet is not yet included and will be part of D5.6. This ensures that stakeholders and TGs have up-to-date access for optimizing their use of digital tools.

3.5.1 Best Practice Booklet

In parallel with the user guides and the real-world examples another important content category that will be implemented is content focused on best practices in order to ensure efficiency, consistency, and alignment with the stakeholders' goals.

The booklet is going to be designed to provide clear, actionable, and practical guidelines that can be consistently implemented and adapted to suit the LEA Officers and experts needs.

By integrating best practices in the training infrastructure, stakeholders can achieve:

- Improved efficiency and productivity
- Enhanced quality of outcomes
- Reduced risk and increased compliance
- Stronger collaboration and alignment across teams

The best practices section is available through the web site and categories and the infrastructure to host the material is implemented in this 1st version (Figure 12).

Figure 12: Training material – Best practices

4. TRAINING MATERIAL

To actively engage stakeholders with the ENIGMA training infrastructure, training manuals are provided as the foundational resource for TG and stakeholder training in

using ENIGMA resources. While the training manuals are concise, well-structured and clear instructional documents, they form a vital bridge between the stakeholders, as the users, and ENIGMA technology. Through clear explanations, engaging visuals and their comprehensible layout, the manuals act as practical training guides and market ENIGMA's identity. Such graphic design and visual communication synergies embed the training manuals in the broader communication strategy of ENIGMA (see D7.2 for more details) which ensures a professional and interconnected presentation of the manuals and tools. As a result, the manuals reinforce the connection between stakeholders and the ENIGMA tools, as an integral part of the public engagement strategy.

4.1 Pedagogy and User-based Training Material

To ensure the ENIGMA training infrastructure is effective and adaptable to the professional needs of stakeholders, ENIGMA incorporates a flipped learning model grounded in Bloom's Taxonomy [3]. Traditionally, classroom learning has been teacher-controlled in the 'all-size fits all philosophy.' While engaging with professionals and stakeholders with different areas of expertise, such training models outlive their usefulness. In contrast, the flipped learning model reverses such instructions where skills attainment, the content, and the pace are controlled by the user [1]. Thus, flipped learning empowers stakeholders to engage in self-directed skills attainment processes and use the ENIGMA training tools according to their specific needs and requirements. Further details on the curricular pedagogies are provided in Deliverable D7.4 and fall outside of D5.5's scope. Such training provision incorporates digital learning for professional needs [4]. To ensure accessibility and user engagement, training formats such as VR avatar walkthroughs, videos, PDFs, and potentially interactive quizzes are designed to meet different learning needs and environments, enhancing engagement and accessibility to a diverse array of learners.

4.2 Training Manuals

To accommodate diverse user preferences and learning styles, ENIGMA's training infrastructure includes conventional handbook-style manuals alongside the VR classroom. The training manuals serve as the foundational resource of the training infrastructure, equipping users with the skills needed to effectively utilize the ENIGMA tools. Each manual offers a structured, step-by-step guide to the platform's features, supporting stakeholders in integrating ENIGMA tools into their daily operations. By

offering a range of training formats, ENIGMA ensures inclusivity and accessibility for all stakeholders, as an intrinsic means of public engagement. For consistency, the ENIGMA tools use the same template (Figure 13) to ensure a recognizable brand for easy recognition by users and is reproducible and made available in PDF.

Figure 13. Overview of the ENIGMA Template for the instruction manuals.

As part of ENIGMA's comprehensive branding and user engagement strategy (see D7.2 for further details on communication and dissemination), ENIGMA developed a detailed manual to guide users on how to use each ENIGMA tool. Beyond its instructional value, the manual reinforces ENIGMA's brand identity through a clear, concise layout applicable to all tools. The consistent design and layout for all manuals aim to visually align the ENIGMA brand which allow stakeholders and TGs to recognise the material as ENIGMA. The individual training manuals are appended with this document. Each manual is tailored to address stakeholder functionalities, enabling users to leverage these tools effectively within the ENIGMA platform.

4.2 Future Potential

Currently, the consortium is testing and implementing a semi-dynamic VR training infrastructure featuring an avatar-guided walkthrough of ENIGMA tools through a cycle of workshops to adapt the training infrastructure to future user needs. The intent of the user-based platform is to offer participants a heightened sense of control and engagement within the environment. It provides a user-friendly and flexible framework that accommodates multiple training formats, including VR experiences, video tutorials, and downloadable PDFs. Yet The ENIGMA VR training environment holds the potential to evolve into a fully dynamic system, where tailored training packages can be further customized to individual users [2]. Such a progression could enhance end-user utility while potentially advancing public engagement. The platform is designed to support future integration of 3D content, paving the way for a fully immersive learning experience (e.g., by adding 3D DTs of CGs as part of the training environment).

The ENIGMA platform successfully integrated core functionalities and demonstrated its usability through extensive testing and stakeholder feedback. The next phase involves iterative improvements, incorporating user acceptance testing, targeted feature expansions, and the integration of additional tools in preparation for full-scale deployment. These enhancements aim to establish the ENIGMA platform as a comprehensive and robust solution for CH preservation and protection. Upon project completion, working groups and FAQ threads can be introduced to maintain stakeholder engagement and public interaction. As a result, the ENIGMA platform could grow and evolve according to user demands. With its innovative approach and strategic roadmap, ENIGMA allows for the monitoring and tracking of illicitly traded CGs. By supporting global efforts to safeguard humanity's shared history, it contributes to a sustainable and technologically advanced framework for addressing the challenges of CH preservation.

5. APPENDICES

Please find all user manuals appended to this document.

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ENIGMA

Endorsing safeguarding, protection, and
provenance management of cultural heritage

3D Reconstruction Tool Manual

User Guide of LEA Officers and Experts

ENIGMA Project

Project title	Endorsing safeguarding, protection, and provenance management of cultural heritage
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Abbreviations

Term	Explanation
CGs	Cultural Goods
CH	Cultural Heritage
DO	Demonstration, Dissemination & Exploitation Objectives
EC	European Commission
PC	Project Coordinator
TG	Target Group
WP	Work Package

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The 3D Generation application is designed to assist customs officers and cultural heritage (CH) experts in analyzing and reconstructing fragmented or damaged CH objects. The platform provides three primary functionalities:

1. 2D Assembly of Objects with Fragmented Parts
2. 2D Damage Detection and Reconstruction of Partly Damaged Objects
3. 3D Model Generation from 2D Images

This manual explains how stakeholders, such as customs officers and archaeologists, can interact with the 3D Generation application when they encounter possible CH objects of interest, such as at airports during baggage check.

1.1 USE CASES

- **Use Case: Customs Officers at Airports**

Capturing Images: Customs officers take 2D photographs of the CH object during baggage checks. The objects can be: a) fragmented, in which case images of individual fragments are required; b) assembled but damaged, a single image capturing the entire object is sufficient.

Uploading Images to the Platform: The custom officer uploads the images to the ENIGMA platform.

Processing with ENIGMA: Depending on the state of the CH object, the 3D Generation application performs different steps: a) Assemble fragments, the application employs artificial intelligence algorithms to assemble fragmented parts into a coherent 3D estimation; b) Detect and reconstruct damage, the applications identifies damage in 2D images and applies automated corrections to reconstruct the object; and c) Generate the final 3D model: the application creates a 3D model from the processed 2D images.

Results Display: The generated 3D model is displayed on-screen for review by the customs officers and CH experts.

- **Image Capture Guidelines**

To ensure accurate reconstruction and processing, the following guidelines must be followed:

Case 1 - Fragments of objects with one visible face (e.g., frescoes): Take clear, high-resolution (i.e., at least 1920x1080 pixels) pictures of each fragment's front face. Ensure the camera is positioned directly in front of the object to avoid distortion. Use adequate lighting to avoid shadows or glare. A flash can be used if it *does not* create reflective spots. Place the fragment against a neutral, non-distracting background (e.g., white or black) to enhance contrast. Save the images as JPEG or PNG (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Fragments of a frescoes

Case 2 – Fragments of objects with Multiple faces (e.g., vases or bowls): Capture clear, high-resolution (i.e., at least 1920x1080 pixels) images of both the outside and inside of each fragment. Begin by photographing one side of the fragments (e.g., the outside), ensuring the camera is positioned directly in front of the surface to avoid distortion. Once all fragments have been photographed from this side, turn each fragment over and capture images of the other side (e.g., the inside). Use adequate lighting to eliminate shadows or glare; a flash can be used if it does not create reflective spots. Place the fragment against a neutral, non-distracting background (e.g., white or black) to enhance contrast. Save the images in a common, high-quality format, such as JPEG or PNG (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Fragments of a vase. On the top of the image, it is possible to see the outside of the fragments. On the bottom of the image, it is possible to see the inside of the fragment.

Case 3 – Assembled but damaged objects: Take a single, high-resolution (i.e., at least 1920x1080 pixels) image that clearly shows the entire object, including all visible damaged areas. Position the camera directly in front of the object to avoid distortion. Use adequate lighting to highlight the damage without creating shadows or glare; a flash can be used if it does not cause reflective spots. Place the object against a neutral, non-distracting background (e.g., white or black) to ensure the damage is visible and stands out. Save the image as JPEG or PNG. See Figure 3 as an example.

Figure 3: Assembled object with visible damage.

1.2 RESULTS DISPLAY GUIDELINES

The display interface allows stakeholders to interact with the 3D model in different manners: a) Rotate and zoom into the 3D model for detailed inspection; b) Compare the reconstructed model with reference images from the database; and c) Download the 3D model for further analysis or documentation. An example of the 3D model is depicted in Figures 4 and 5.

Figure 4: An example of the reconstructed 3D model with multiple faces. In the ENIGMA interface, the user can interact with the object.

Figure 5: An example of the reconstructed 3D model with a single face. In the ENIGMA interface, the user can interact with the object.

1.3 TEST SCENARIOS

Test Scenario 1

Fragmented Vase Reconstruction: The objective of this scenario is to validate the system's ability to accurately assemble and generate a 3D model from fragmented objects with multiple faces.

Steps: 1) from the test data provided, choose the fragments from a ceramic vase with both the pictures from the outside and inside surfaces; 2) upload the chosen data to the ENIGMA platform. To accomplish that, first input the CG details. Then, in the "Upload documents and Photos"

option, add the selected data from Step 1; 3) the system processes the fragments and display the reconstructed 3D model; 4) review the output, verify that all fragments are assembled correctly into the 3D representation.

Test Scenario 2

Damage Detection and Correction: The objective of this scenario is to ensure the system accurately detects and reconstructs damages in assembled CH objects. 1) from the test data provided, choose an assembled ceramic bowl with visible missing parts; 2) upload the chosen data to the ENIGMA platform. To accomplish that, first input the CG details. Then in the "Upload documents and Photos" option, add the selected data from Step 1; 3) The system processes the partially damaged object and displays a reconstructed 2D object with corrected damages and the 3D model of the reconstructed object; 4) review the output, verify that the missing parts in the 2D image are corrected and the 3D model incorporates the reconstructed features.

Test Data

Fragmented Frescoes, Vases, and Bowls: This set of data contains a set of high-resolution images of frescoes, vases, and bowls fragments. For vases and bowls, this includes both outside and inside views. In total, this set will comprise 15 fragmented objects.

Damaged Vases, Bowls, Bust of Statue, Tablet, Stele, and Arrowhead: This set of data contains images of partially damaged vases, bowls, bust of statue, tablet, stele, and arrowhead. In total, this set will comprise 15 partially damaged objects with visible missing parts.

1.4 INSTRUCTIONS FOR INSTRUCTOR

Preparation: Ensure all test data is available and accessible for all the participants.

Training Execution: Demonstrate each action step-by-step, a) show how to capture images following the "Image Capture Guidelines"; b) guide the uploading process of the fragmented and damaged objects to the platform; c) display the final output and explain its significance. Finally, allow participants to practice each test scenario using the provided test datasets.

Assessment: Provide the checklist for trainees to ensure correct execution of each step. Observe and provide real-time feedback during the training. Evaluate the final output and the series of steps taken.

1.5 CHECKLIST FOR TRAINEES

General Preparation:

- Verify access to the ENIGMA platform and ensure trainee login credentials are available.
- Confirm availability of test datasets (e.g., fragmented and partially damaged).
- Ensure the trainee have the equipment to take pictures according to the requirements in the "Image Capture Guideline".

Upload Images:

- Log in to the ENIGMA platform.
- Navigate to the "Upload documents and Photos" option.
- Upload the images to the designated section.

Processing:

- Confirm that the fragments are accounted for in the image preview.
- Confirm that damaged areas can be seen in the image preview.

Output Verification:

- In case of partially damaged objects, inspect the reconstructed 2D image to confirm all damage has been addressed.
- Generate the 3D model and verify how the estimation fits with the appearance of a certain object.

Post-Exercise:

- Complete both test scenarios.
- Provide feedback on platform usability and any challenges faced.
- Submit screenshots, 3D models, and notes to the instruction for evaluation.

1.6 ENIGMA PLATFORM STEP-BY-STEP

LEA Officers:

1. Open the ENIGMA platform and navigate to the Provenance Tool - LEA Screen.
2. Click on the “Add a new CG” button on the left-side menu to initiate the process of adding a new cultural good.
3. After feeling the fields demonstrated in *Figure 6*, click the “Next” button to proceed to the image upload stage.

Figure 7: Upload pictures screen.

5. For fragmented objects, if they have two faces, upload images of both the outside and inside of each fragment following the provided capture guidelines. For partially damaged objects, upload a single image showing the complete object, including all visible damaged areas.
6. As each image is uploaded, it will appear in the preview panel on the right. Ensure the images are: clear, high-resolution (at least 1920x1080 pixels), properly oriented, and free of shadows.
7. Once all required images are uploaded and verified, click the “Save” button to store the object data and images. The, click “Next” to proceed to the next steps, such as automatically generating a 3D model or assigning tasks.

Figure 6: Add a new CG screen.

4. Now in the “Upload documents and photos” step, *Figure 7*, locate the upload section on the right-hand side of the screen. Then, click the “Upload” button to select the pictures of the object.

Archaeologists/Experts

1. Open the ENIGMA platform and navigate to the “Provenance Tool – Archaeologists / Experts” screen.
2. Click on “Assigned Jobs” in the left-side menu to view a list of CGs assigned by LEA officers, as shown in *Figure 8*.

Figure 8: Assigned jobs expert screen.

3. Review the list of assigned items, including the CG ID, Title, Registration Date, and Status.
4. Select an item from the list by clicking the corresponding row to proceed to the evaluation and enrichment process.
5. After selecting an item, the system will display the detailed view in the Details tab, as shown in *Figure 9*.

6. Open the 3D Model tab to review the reconstructed model. If the reconstruction is successful, evaluate the accuracy of the model in comparison to the uploaded images and known attributes. If the reconstruction fails, proceed with the evaluation based on available attributes and data (e.g., material type, dimensions, chronological period).
7. When the 3D reconstruction process fails: a) cross-check the provided attributes (e.g., material, dimensions, chronological period) against known historical and cultural databases; b) use the available images to perform a manual assessment of the object’s condition, damage, and possible provenance; c) document any findings of hypotheses.
8. After completing the evaluation and enrichment process, click “Save” to store the updated data. Then, click “Next” to proceed to the final confirmation step, ensuring all required fields are complete. Lastly, submit the enriched CG record for further review or finalization in the ENIGMA platform.

Figure 9: Job details screen.

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ENIGMA

Endorsing safeguarding, protection, and
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Provenance GUI

User Guide of LEA Officers and Experts

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1.1 INTRODUCTION

The provenance research tool developed within the framework of ENIGMA takes into account the user requirements. This application is comprised of different tools / components and utilizes the output of other services developed within ENIGMA in order to determine the provenance of an object. The provenance research tool exploits the UAI layers developed and defined in to determine the unique “fingerprint” of a registered CG, uses the AI/ML stratification tools and the contextual analysis developed to provide the best prediction of an unknown CG “fingerprint”. The tool also exploits the scenario building engine to overcome semantic reasoning heterogeneity of support data and documents, uses the output ENIGMA decision support system to incorporate metadata cross-checking and automatic matching with various CH database, and exploits the input from public engagement (crowd sourcing app) to scale up the search range. Furthermore, alerts generated by the Earth Observation toolkit, are used to refine the performed queries and provide clearer results regarding the provenance of CGs.

This user guide focuses on introducing the provenance web interface and its functionalities to the end users, in order to support the main goal of the provenance tool.

The end users are divided in two groups:

- The LEA officers
- The Experts (Archaeologist and other)

1.2 GETTING STARTED

The provenance tool is a web based accessible interface that doesn't have any system-based requirements for using the tool.

The only requirement is to register at the ENIGMA platform and get assigned with the appropriate role (LEA or Expert) by the system administrator.

• Getting access to the system

The users have to register through the main enigma platform web interface. The landing page is the following (figure 1):

<https://enigma.cellock.com>

Figure 1: Main ENIGMA platform landing page

The users have to select the “Login/register” option on the top menu to access the section regarding the signing up process or login (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Signup and login option tab

If the users get access to the interface for the first time, they need to sign up and the administrator will assign the appropriate user role (LEA officer or Expert).

• Sign up process

The users need to provide the following information to request access:

1. First Name
2. Last name
3. E-mail
4. Password

The prerequisites for the password are the following:

- Password has at least 8 characters.
- Password has special characters.
- Password has a number.
- Password has a capital letter.
- Passwords match.

The user interface for the signup process is presented in the following image (Figure 3).

Signup with your email

Please fill in the details below

First name *

Last name *

Email *

Code *

Password *

Confirm Password *

- ✗ Password has at least 8 characters.
- ✗ Password has special characters.
- ✗ Password has a number.
- ✗ Password has a capital letter.
- ✗ Passwords match.

Sign Up

By pressing Send request, you agree that we may contact you via phone/text and/or email about your inquiry, which may involve the use of automated means. You also agree to our Terms of Use

Figure 3: Signup form

2.1 USER INTERFACE OVERVIEW

The experts after their authentication are getting access to the ENIGMA platform tools under a unified environment. In the left panel the users have access to the tools that their role is entitled to access. In this case the experts have access to the provenance research tool, to the earth observation analysis results tool, and the crowdsourcing analysis tool (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Navigation panel for Experts access

• **Description of the main components of the interface**

In the provenance research tool the Archaeologists/experts have the ability to review all the CG cases assigned to them and provide further information to the system using the fast documentation module and get access to the images, 3D content in parallel with additional tools that incorporated insights based on the UAI similarity checking process, AI/ML module and the joint data workspace that provides access to various sources. Furthermore, access to the earth observation toolkit and crowdsourcing analysis tool provide more information in the field for the potential origin areas.

• **Explanation of icons, buttons, and menus**

The tool has 3 main sections the navigation area, the main editing and analysis screens section, and the searching areas. The user can select the section of the tool to work on by selecting it from the navigation area (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Navigation section of the provenance tool

In each section that the end user will need to perform a query to a list of multiple objects has on top of the screen a search panel to filter out the necessary objects based on specific characteristics/parameters (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Navigation section of the provenance tool

The screens where the end users can edit and analyse information provide them with “Buttons” to move forward to the workflow process “Next” or to go back “Back” (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Action Buttons supporting the process and the expert’s work

Furthermore, the end users have the “Save” option to save the corresponding edited information of the current screen (Figure 8).

Figure 8: “Save” Button for the edited information

The end users can go back and forth to the screens and also navigate to the additional tools “Similarity checking”, “Remote Sensing Alerts” and “Crowdsourcing Analysis Tool” (cf. Figure 5).

2.2 BASIC OPERATIONS

The experts are involved in the process when the LEA officers assign to them a CG for further investigation. In this context the experts have access to several tools to work and provide feedback to the LEA officers. The basic tools that the experts have access are the following:

- **Assignment management form**
- **CG documentation forms**
- **Provenance analysis and UAI based similar objects**
- **Remote sensing alerts**
- **Crowdsourcing analysis**

2.3 BASIC OPERATIONS – EXPERTS

The experts start their analysis process from the page where the list of assigned objects are provided by the LEA Officer. The experts have access only to the objects that are assigned to them.

- **Assignment management form**

The experts can search and select from the interface the CG object they are going to work on. The form provides some searching parameters to filter the list of the assigned objects (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Assignment management form

The experts select the CG that they are going to work with and choose the option to access and edit the already provided information (from the LEA Officer) (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Button to select and edit CG information

Following the selection of the CG that requires further investigation, the experts are guided

through the interface to the screens where they can provide additional and more detailed information regarding the CG documentation.

- **CG documentation forms**

The provenance research tool is structured in a way that enables the experts to provide additional information to better document the CG. In the details form the experts can add information regarding the CG. The main categories of information are the **General** information regarding the description of the object, the type, the material etc., the **Places** where different type of places (provenance, excavated from, current location, coverage etc.) associated to the object can be recorded, the **Chronological Periods** to cover the timespan of the period that the object comes from, issued or related to etc., the **Dimensions** of the object, and the **Agents** (organizations or persons) that stand for different type of relationship with the object (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Screen to manage CG object detail features

Important remark: When the features to be edited has a standardized list of values the UI provides a

search button like the one on Figure 12. This button lists proposed standardized vocabulary values from Getty and other sources.

Figure 12: Search button to get proposed standardized vocabulary values from Getty and other resources

In the section of the CG fast documentation process the provenance research tool provides the end users with the ability to access, download and view any documents that the LEA Officer has provided. They can also upload additional documents (Figure 13).

Figure 13: Documents navigation, view or upload functionality

The next screen in the CG documentation form contains the section regarding images of the CG under investigation. The experts can access the images that the LEA Officer provided in order to get additional information (Figures 14 and 15).

Figure 14: Images navigation, view or upload functionality

Figure 15: 3D navigation, view or upload functionality

The detailed documentation of the object and the overall required information provision is an iterative process that needs research and further investigation from the experts. The additional insights regarding the object are provided to the experts by the following tools: the UAI similarity checking tool, the earth observation alerts results and the crowdsourcing analysis tool.

- **Provenance analysis and UAI based similar objects**

While the archaeologists/experts research and investigate the object they can access and view similar objects that the system provides from the joint workspace. The joint workspace migrates information of CG objects of multiple databases and crawled data. In the process to understand and recognize the object's provenance the end users can iteratively add and enrich the features of the CG and access the similarity checking tool to view suggestions of similar objects. Using this approach the users access multiple similar objects with the corresponding similarity score. They can view the objects' images, access the related information in the source and get "help" to decide and recognize the objects' provenance. The system provides the most similar CGs to the one that is under investigation and the users can search, filter and change the features' importance to get better similarity results (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Similarity process and results from the joint workspace

Important notice: The tool brings the most similar objects based on the data that have been recorded through the CG documentation forms. The more information the experts provide the more accurate the similarity checking process will be.

- **Earth observation alerts**

In parallel the experts have access to the earth observation analysis tool that provides potential illegal excavation areas. The tool focuses on areas that are provided by the experts as the possible origin of the object. The areas are highlighted by a red boundary polygon (Figure 17).

Figure 17: Remote Sensing analysis alerts for possible illegal excavation areas.

The tool incorporates several additional tools for searching locations, and navigating to the map such as zoom in, zoom out, previous view, measurement tools and changing basemaps options (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Map navigation and searching tools

- **Crowdsourcing analysis**

The crowdsourcing analysis tool provides analyzed information that comes from the public engagement tool. The public have access to a web app (responsive design-mobile accessible app) where they can add and upload geolocated images of potential illegal excavations or damaged monuments and the system can highlight the areas with high issues concentration. These areas, if they are near to the potential provenance / origin of the CG under investigation, give insights for the experts to draw more accurate conclusions (Figure 19).

Figure 19: Map crowd data hot spot analysis

As soon as the experts decide whether the CG is stolen or not, or need further investigation, they can use the tool to flag the object and inform the involved parties, LEA Officers, or other experts where they can reassign the object for further investigation. If the experts recognize the provenance of the object and it originates from a foreign country, they proceed to communicate with the corresponding authorities. In this case they have the ability to reassign the object (Figures 20 and 21).

Figure 20: Assignment to other expert form

Figure 21: Flag the CG as stolen or not

2.4 ADVANCED FEATURES

- **INSTRUCTIONS TO UTILIZE PROVENANCE TOOLS AND UAI SIMILAR OBJECTS**

The end users retrieve similar objects based on the UAI and the similarity checking algorithm. In order for the experts to retrieve more calibrated / accurate results they have access to the feature importance management controls and searching panel to apply filters (weights) to the overall dataset provided from the main ENIGMA database (Figure 22).

Figure 22: Management controls to access similar objects and filter out based on additional knowledge.

2.5 FAQ AND TROUBLESHOOTING

1. How is the role of the users going to be assigned?

As soon as the users are registered, they have to contact the System administrator and assign the corresponding role. The administrator assigns the role, and the users get access to the provided tools.

2. What is the source of the information that the similarity checking process provides?

The similarity checking process accesses the joint workspace (ENIGMA graph DB) where all the data are hosted and runs the necessary algorithm to recognize the most similar objects to the one that is under investigation.

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Earth Observation Toolkit Manual

User Guide of cultural heritage authorities,
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1.1 INTRODUCTION

ENIGMA is a cutting-edge geospatial monitoring platform designed to detect and prevent illegal excavation activities using advanced remote sensing automation. By leveraging satellite imagery, advanced image processing, and GIS technology, ENIGMA enables authorities and experts to monitor high-risk areas across multiple regions.

With an intuitive interface, users can:

- Identify and mark suspicious areas – Easily highlight regions of interest to guide the remote sensing analysis algorithms to focus on specific areas.
- Analyze multitemporal satellite imagery and pinpoint potential illegal digging for enhanced situational awareness.
- Get alerts and reporting – Receive instant updates on unusual land activity and ground anomalies.

The ENIGMA Earth Observation (EO) toolkit empowers governments, LEA authorities and archaeologists, with the EO toolkit needed to safeguard cultural heritage and support the prevention of illegal excavation.

1.2 THE PLATFORM

• BACKEND DETAILS

The backend of the EO toolkit is hosted on the ECoE server, where all computational operations are processed. It is built using scalable and efficient server-side technologies, optimized for handling large-scale geospatial data and complex computational workflows. The backend is designed to integrate seamlessly with EO datasets and analysis libraries, ensuring high performance and reliability. Key functionalities include data ingestion and fetching, processing, and storage, powered by advanced algorithms and frameworks tailored for EO and remote sensing tasks. The

system also features robust APIs for interoperability and extensibility, allowing for smooth communication between the server and client-side components.

• FRONTEND DETAILS

The frontend is integrated within the ENIGMA platform, offering a clean, intuitive web-based interface for user interaction.

Built with modern web technologies, the frontend provides a responsive and dynamic user experience.

System's access is provided to two main categories of users:

- **Authorities responsible for cultural heritage monitoring** can design and define specific areas that should be monitored in timely manner.
- **End users (LEA officers and archaeologists/experts to monitor the alerts)** can perform data exploration, search and visualize the results directly through their browser.

Given the sensitivity of the processed information, a key component of the frontend is its robust authentication system, which ensures secure access to the platform.

User credentials are verified through a secure authentication process, integrated with the ENIGMA platform's role-based access control system. This ensures that only authorized users can access specific features and datasets, safeguarding sensitive operations and data integrity.

1.3 GETTING STARTED

The EO toolkit is a web based, accessible interface with no specific system-based requirement for use.

The only prerequisite is to register on the ENIGMA platform and be assigned an appropriate role (CH authorities, LEA or Expert) by the system administrator.

• GETTING ACCESS TO THE SYSTEM

The users have to register through the main ENIGMA platform web interface. The landing page is the following (Figure 1):

<https://enigma.cellock.com>

Figure 1: Main ENIGMA platform landing page

The users have to select the “Login/register” option on the top menu to access the section regarding the signing up process or login (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Signup and login option tab

If the users get access to the interface for the first time, they need to sign up and the administrator will assign the appropriate user role (cultural heritage authority, LEA officer or Expert).

• Sign up process

The users need to provide the following information to request access:

5. First Name
6. Last name
7. E-mail
8. Password

The prerequisites for the password are the following:

- Password has at least 8 characters.
- Password has special characters.
- Password has a number.
- Password has a capital letter.
- Passwords match.

The user interface for the signup process is presented in the following image (Figure 3).

Signup with your email
Please fill in the details below

- ✗ Password has at least 8 characters.
- ✗ Password has special characters.
- ✗ Password has a number.
- ✗ Password has a capital letter.
- ✗ Passwords match.

Sign Up

By pressing Send request, you agree that we may contact you via phone/text and/or email about your inquiry, which may involve the use of automated means. You also agree to our [Terms of Use](#)

Figure 3: Signup form

2.1 USER INTERFACE OVERVIEW

The users, based on their role, are granted access to different interfaces. CH authorities receive access to the EO toolkit management interface whereas LEA Officers and archaeology/experts to the interface that highlights the results-alerts generated by the remote sensing scientific analysis.

In the left panel, users can access the tools available to them based on their assigned role. If users are designated as responsible personnel from CH authorities to manage the monitored areas, they will have access to the Remote Sensing Management tool.

Experts having access to the provenance research tool they can also find the remote sensing alerts interface integrated. In parallel the same interface is provided as stand-alone application (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Navigation panel for Experts access

DESCRIPTION OF THE MAIN SECTIONS OF THE REMOTE SENSING MANAGEMENT INTERFACE

The interface consists of:

- **Left Panel:** Navigation menu with options such as "Checking Areas" and "Alert Areas".
- **Main Map View:** Displays near-real-time satellite imagery of monitored locations.
- **Right Panel:** A list of regions categorized by geographical areas, such as Cyprus, Malta, and Greece etc.

EXPLANATION OF ICONS, BUTTONS, AND MENUS

The interface has two main sections. One which allows to manage and navigate the interactive map and the second to edit and manage areas of interest (Figure 5):

- **Home Icon (🏠):** Returns to the initial extent of the map.
- **Search Icon (🔍):** Allows users to search for specific locations or coordinates.
- **Basemaps Icon (🗺️):** Toggles between different map views (satellite, terrain, hybrid).
- **Zoom In (+) and Zoom Out (-):** Adjust the map view for better level of detail.

Manage and edit areas Interaction buttons

- **Select Region:** Click on a highlighted area to view additional information and analysis.
- **Edit Feature:** Opens a dialog box to annotate or update information on a flagged area.
- **Create Feature:** Allows users to mark and document a suspicious activity on the map.

Figure 5: General overview of the authorities' management user interface

2.2 BASIC OPERATIONS

The responsible authority users can add, remove or edit specific polygons on the map to designate areas for monitoring by the EO toolkit. Moreover, they have the ability to get an overview and navigate to the pinpointed areas. The basic operations that the authorities can access are the following:

- **MANAGE AREAS OF INTEREST**
- **VIEW ALERT AREAS THAT HAVE BEEN CREATED THROUGH EO TOOLKIT BACKEND**

2.3 BASIC OPERATIONS – CULTURAL HERITAGE AUTHORITIES

The end users can navigate the map, manage monitored areas and review the alerts provided by the automated remote sensing process.

- **MONITORED AREAS MANAGEMENT FORM**
The experts can navigate the map using the buttons provided (zoom, change basemap, search areas) and, as soon as they find an area of interest (AOI), they can use the edit button (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Edit areas for monitoring

The end users should select whether to edit an existing AOI (A) or add a new one (B) (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Button to select or edit monitored areas

In the case that they are going to draw a new AOI they should go to the map →, draw a polygon, and add a short description (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Form to edit description of the Area of Interest

Although the EO toolkit will compute the change detection according with the users' input, and regardless the extension of the AOI, it is highly advised to define the boundaries of the archaeological sites as precise as possible.

Once the areas of interest are defined, the backend automatically process them as scheduled. Algorithms process the selected data and provides the alert results, which are then made available for visualization.

- **VIEW ALERT AREAS THAT HAVE BEEN CREATED THROUGH EO TOOLKIT BACKEND**

The users have the ability to review the Remote Sensing analysis outcomes selecting from the left side panel the map with the alerts (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Map accessing the alerts provided by the EO toolkit

2.4 BASIC OPERATIONS – THE END USERS LEADERS AND ARCHAEOLOGISTS/EXPERTS

The users that manage the CG recognition and documentation using the provenance tool can access only the alerted areas from the provenance web interface.

The EO tool focuses on areas that are provided from the expert as the possible provenance of the object. The areas are highlighted by red boundary polygon (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Remote Sensing analysis alerts for possible illegal excavation areas

The EO toolkit incorporates several additional features for searching location and/or navigating through the map such as zoom in, zoom out, previous view, measurement tools and changing basemaps option (Figure 11).

Figure 11: Map navigation and searching tools

Funded by
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ENIGMA

Endorsing safeguarding, protection, and
provenance management of cultural heritage

Scenario Building Engine Manual

User Guide of LEA Officers and Experts

ENIGMA Project

Project title	Endorsing safeguarding, protection, and provenance management of cultural heritage
Project acronym	ENIGMA
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Manual name	Scenario Building Engine User Guide_v0.1
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Abbreviations

Term	Explanation
CGs	Cultural Goods
CH	Cultural Heritage
DO	Demonstration, Dissemination & Exploitation Objectives
EC	European Commission
PC	Project Coordinator
TG	Target Group
WP	Work Package

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The **Scenario Building Engine (SBE)** is a series of tasks, activities, or steps that are organized in a logical sequence to accomplish a specific goal or objective within a business or organizational process. Workflows are designed to streamline and standardize the execution of tasks, ensuring that they are carried out in a consistent and efficient manner. The SBE tool is dedicated to higher level **LEA officers**, who in collaboration with **archaeologists** and other experts, can better assess and improve the overall workflow performance.

The SBE allows higher-level LEA officers, archaeologists, and other experts to collaborate effectively and improve overall workflow performance. Key characteristics of workflows include sequential order, role allocation, decision points, automation, feedback mechanisms, and progress monitoring.

The SBE is a comprehensive platform that integrates decision-making, automation, and monitoring, ensuring that every workflow operates at peak efficiency. By providing users with tailored metrics and tools, SBE enables informed decisions, improving operational outcomes across various scenarios.

1.1 KEY CHARACTERISTICS OF A WORKFLOW

The key characteristics of a workflow include:

- **Sequential order:** Tasks arranged in a specific sequence
- **Roles and responsibilities:** specific roles allocation with the responsibility of executing each task
- **Conditions and decision points:** Workflows incorporate decision points where specific conditions are evaluated
- **Automation:** tasks automation within a workflow

- **Feedback and communication:** Mechanisms for communication, notifications, and feedback loops
- **Monitoring and control:** Continuous monitoring progress tracking
- **Status and transitions:** State or condition of a task and movement or change of status from one state to another

Here follows an example scenario to better understand how SBE operates (*Figure 1*): let us take a scenario where a statue is discovered in a passenger’s luggage arriving from -for example- Libya and Maltese border control officers took immediate steps to determine its legitimacy and take appropriate actions using ENIGMA tools. The workflow is presented in the following diagram where various steps are defined. The goal is to facilitate decision-making and ensure that all tasks are completed with accountability.

Figure 1: Sample Workflow

Actions like initial discovery, logging the item, consulting experts, and reaching a decision are organized logically. Roles such as border officers, archaeologists, or supervisors are assigned

responsibilities for each step. This workflow can be simulated in SBE allowing continuous tracking of the process, enabling timely interventions or escalations if needed.

1.2 BUILDING A WORKFLOW TEMPLATE

Building a workflow in SBE involves creating a logical sequence of tasks, assigning roles, defining conditions, and incorporating automation where possible. SBE workflows are built on fundamental entities such as tasks, roles, conditions, and metrics. Each entity plays a crucial role in constructing workflows that are both efficient and adaptable to changing needs. Status and transitions are a critical aspect of workflows managed within SBE. Each transition is governed by privileges assigned to roles. For example, only authorized personnel can approve specific transitions and that’s how we ensure the integrity of the process.

Creating workflows in the SBE environment is a structured process that ensures every workflow is fully customizable and aligned with organizational goals. Let us go through the steps involved in detail.

1.3 CREATE STATUSES

First of all, create the different statuses within the workflow (*Figure 2*). Statuses represent the stages or steps a task goes through, such as “CG Validated”, “Pending Review”, “Details”, “In Progress”, or “Completed”. Each status is critical to track progress and organize tasks effectively.

Figure 2: Create Status

The list of already created statuses is presented in the following screenshot (*Figure 3*):

ID ↓	Name
18	Assignment
17	Success
16	Confirmation
15	3D model
14	Images
13	Documents
12	Holder
11	Transportation
10	Details

Figure 3: Statuses list

1.4 CREATE A NEW WORKFLOW TYPE

Proceed to create a New Workflow Type in order to define the type of workflow to be created. This involves naming the workflow type and identifying its purpose.

For instance, it could be a workflow for the provenance of a CG, archaeological artifact processing, or another use case.

[Workflow Management](#) + [Create new workflow type](#)

Using the already defined statuses, the user can set the initial and the final status of the workflow to be created (Figure 4). Also, roles that can create an instance of this workflow should be defined here.

The following roles are available to the user:

- LEA Officer
- RS Administration Authority
- Cultural Administration Authority
- Archeologist
- User
- Admin

This step acts as the foundation of the workflow.

Figure 4: Workflow Type

1.5 WORKFLOW TRANSITIONS

Next, create the Workflow Transitions (Figure 5). Once the statuses are in place, define the transitions between them. Transitions specify how tasks move from one status to another. For instance, a task might move from “Pending Review” to “Approved” after an officer verifies its details. Transitions can also include conditions, ensuring they occur only when specific criteria are met.

[Workflow Management](#) + [Create workflow transition](#)

Figure 5: Workflow Transitions

1.6 WORKFLOW PRIVILEGES

Finally, create the Workflow Privileges (Figure 6). This involves determining who has the authority to execute specific transitions or access certain statuses. For example, only a supervisor might be able to move a task to “Completed”.

[Workflow Management](#) + [Create workflow privilege](#)

Figure 6: Workflow Privileges

By following the above steps, SBE ensures that workflows are not only structured and efficient but also secure and adaptable to various operational needs.

1.7 CREATING A WORKFLOW INSTANCE

After creating a workflow template, the user can generate an instance of the workflow (Figure 7). The list of already created workflow instances is listed in the following screenshot when the user selects the “Workflows” option:

[Workflows](#)

ID	Type	Status
21	Provenance Tool workflow 1	3D model
20	Pilot case 4 Workflow	Transportation
19	Pilot case 4 Workflow	Transportation
18	Pilot case 4 Workflow	Transportation
17	Pilot case 4 Workflow	Confirmation
16	Pilot case 4 Workflow	Images
15	Pilot case 4 Workflow	Holder
14	Pilot case 4 Workflow	Holder
13	Pilot case 4 Workflow	Holder
12	Pilot case 4 Workflow	Holder
11	Pilot case 4 Workflow	Documents

Figure 7: Workflows instances

By selecting the option “Create Workflow” the user can create a new workflow instance based on an already created workflow template (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Create Workflow

1.8 RUN/EDIT A WORKFLOW INSTANCE

By pressing the icon in the workflow’s instances list, the user can edit the workflow instance (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Editing a workflow instance

The workflow diagram and status are displayed by pressing the “History” option.

Figure 10: Workflow diagram

Figure 10 shows that the user edits the Transportation status for proceeding to the next status (“Holder”) by applying to the “Submit Transportation” data transition button.

1.9 METRICS

At Metrics, the core of informed decision-making, the user/stakeholder will have the ability to view and analyze real-time metrics. This enables stakeholders, such as LEAs, archaeologists, and other experts, to assess the effectiveness and efficiency of workflows. This feature is particularly valuable for monitoring progress, identifying bottlenecks, and making data-driven adjustments.

For example, let us imagine a workflow where officers are inspecting a shipment of artifacts (Figure 11). Metrics such as task completion rates, average processing times, and the number of items flagged for further review can provide critical insights. These metrics allow stakeholders to identify stages where delays occur, or where additional resources might be required, ensuring smoother operations. Metrics in SBE are not just static reports, they are interactive and dynamic. Users will be able to filter and customize the data to focus on what matters most for their specific role or responsibility. Additionally, historical data trends can inform long-term strategies and help predict potential challenges.

Figure 11: Metrics (LEA officers)

Similarly, archaeologists and subject matter experts benefit from SBE’s metrics, which provide detailed insights into specific workflows (Figure 12). These metrics support thorough analysis and effective collaboration.

Figure 12: Metrics (Experts)